

1 **An asymmetric cell division program endogenous to the oocyte.**

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7 We used transcriptional similarity algorithms to discover components of an asymmetric cell division
8 program endogenous to the oocyte. The components functioned in a network in addition to known ACD
9 program effectors Aph1a and Pof1b. Cell division decisions that are meiotic in nature are thus expected to
10 be specialized and oocyte-specific. Information on specialized ACD programs is limited.

11 Citations

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